

Questionnaire on the Universal Design for Learning (UDL) Study

This questionnaire aims to explore the extent of implementation of Universal Design for Learning (UDL) in the pedagogical practices of Chilean teachers, considering their perceptions of diversity and the professional training they have received in this model. Additionally, it seeks to identify teachers' training needs in order to strengthen their pedagogical practices and optimize their professional performance in the classroom.

Instructions:

- Complete Item A with an X, providing demographic information and details about the school context where you work.
- Next, Item B presents a series of statements about UDL characteristics and pedagogical practices framed within the model's development. Please respond honestly, as your answers are confidential and anonymous.

A. DEMOGRAPHIC AND SCHOOL CONTEXT INFORMATION

A.1. Educational institution:

Name of the school

Type of school	Public	Private-subsidized	Private
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Contextual Vulnerability	Greater than 60% vulnerability"	Less than 60% vulnerability
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A.2 Participants:

Gender	Male	Female	Non-binary	Other
Age	25-34 years	35-44 years	45-54 years	55 more or years
Initial Training	Primary Education Teacher	Secondary Education Teacher	Special Education Teacher	Other professionals
Years of Professional Experience	0-4 years	5-8 years	9-12 years	13 more or years
Role held in the classroom	Classroom Teacher		Special Education Teacher	
Teaching Education Level	Primary Education		Secondary Education	

A.3 Perception of Diversity: Based on your classroom experience, indicate the educational support needs present in your class, where 1 means “very little” and 5 means “a lot.”

	Almost nothing (1)	A little (2)	Moderate (3)	Quite a lot (4)	A lot (5)
Attention Deficit Hyperactivity Disorder (ADHD)					
Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD)					
Language Disorder (LD)					
Migrant students					

A.3.1 If your answer includes another educational support need, please specify which one

A.4 Professional training: Select the type of professional training you have in UDL

Type of training in UDL	No training	Initial training	Continuing training	Self-Taught

A.4.1 Only answer this section if you selected the ‘Continuing Education in UDL’ option

Type of UDL Specialization	No training	Course o workshop	Diploma Program	Post certificate program	Graduate program (Postgraduate)
Number of Training Hours	None	Less Than 20 hours	Between 20 and 60 hours	Between 60 and 100 hours	More than 100 hours
Funding Source	No funding	School	Own funds	CPEIP Centro de Experimentación e Innovación pedagógica	Scholarships

B. PEDAGOGICAL PRACTICES AND UNIVERSAL DESIGN FOR LEARNING (UDL):

Instructions: The following statements concern the development of pedagogical practices aligned with the principles of the UDL model. Please rate, on a Likert scale from 1 to 5, the extent to which you incorporate this approach into your classroom practices. Use the following scale to assign your score:

Scale

1. **Never:** I do not incorporate it into my professional practice.
2. **Rarely:** I incorporate it sporadically into my professional practice.
3. **Sometimes:** I incorporate it moderately into my professional practice.
4. **Frequently:** I incorporate it significantly into my professional practice.
5. **Always:** I fully incorporate it into my professional practice.

B.1 PEDAGOGICAL PRACTICES AND UDL: Mark with an X the box that represents the extent to which you incorporate UDL in your teaching practice, where 1 = Never and 5 = Always.		1	2	3	4	5
MULTIPLE MEANS OF ENGAGEMENT	C1. I promote freedom of choice and autonomous work. (7.2)					
	C2. I provide various options to motivate learning, taking into account my students' creativity, identity, and interests. (7.2)					
	C3. "I encourage play and a respectful learning environment (7.3)					
	C4. I address biases and minimize threats and distractions in the classroom. (7.4)					
	C5. I maintain effort and consistency by modeling and scaffolding learning objectives, activities, and achievement indicators according to my students' characteristics. (8.1)					
	C6. I facilitate strategies or procedures to scaffold and optimize learning challenges. (8.2)					
	C7. I promote peer collaboration and collective learning. (8.3)					
	C8. I foster a sense of belonging to the community (8.4)					
	C9. I provide consistent and in-depth feedback on my students' performance using instruments based on measurable indicators. (8.5)					
	C10. I identify my students' expectations, beliefs, and motivations. (9.1)					
	C11. I establish behavioral guidelines and conflict-resolution methods agreed upon with the group. (9.2)					

	C12. I promote strategies for emotional self-regulation and both group and individual reflection in students. (9.3)					
	C13. I foster empathetic and meaningful interpersonal relationships with my students (9.4)					
MULTIPLE MEANS OF REPRESENTATION	R14. I use the whiteboard and adapt the information in textbooks and written materials to facilitate perception and understanding. (1.1)					
	R15. I design personalized and innovative learning experiences with the support of ICT, creating manipulable or interactive materials that facilitate students' perception of information. (1.2)					
	R16. The selected educational materials consider diverse perspectives, identities, and cultures. (1.3)					
	R17. I frequently clarify the vocabulary, symbols, and linguistic structure of the materials or instructional resources. (2.1)					
	R18. I use additional educational resources to support the understanding of texts, mathematical notations, and symbols. (2.2)					
	R19. I promote understanding of and respect for languages and cultural differences. (2.3)					
	R20. I address biases in the use of language and symbols to ensure proper access to information. (2.4)					
	R21. I illustrate information in various media of representation according to the learning paces and styles of my students. (2.5)					
	R22. I develop new knowledge by connecting it with my students' prior learning. (3.1)					
	R23. I illustrate patterns, characteristics, main ideas, and relationships within knowledge. (3.2)					
	R24. I develop active methodologies that enable the assignment of new meanings to knowledge. (3.3)					
	R25. I create challenging learning situations that enable students to apply and transfer information to other contexts. (3.4)					
MULTIPLE MEANS OF ACTION AND EXPRESSION	A26. I diversify assessment and interaction methods through concept maps, collaborative work, gamification, among others. (4.1)					
	A27. I provide access to materials, technologies, and assistive tools to interact during learning. (4.2)					
	A28. I establish diverse forms of expression and communication of learning, such as verbal, written, graphic, exams, debates, among others. (5.1)					

	A29. facilitate various tools for the construction of creative knowledge through platforms and interactive applications such as Canva or Kahoot, Project- or Problem-Based Learning, creative writing, and Art or design projects. (5.2)					
	A30. I gradually develop students' skills through practical learning activities. (5.3)					
	A31. I addressed biases in the modes of expression and communication of learning. (5.4)					
	A32. I establish meaningful objectives according to my students' interests and competencies. (6.1)					
	A33. I develop strategies to plan objectives and anticipate challenges (6.2)					
	A34. I organize information and resources to optimize learning. (6.3)					
	A35. "I effectively monitor my students' learning progress. (6.4)					
	A36. I reflect critically and inclusively on my teaching practices. (6.5)					